

SET EXPRESSIONS AND IDIOMS

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Abstract: This article gives information on set -expressions and idioms. But no matter what their meaning these are studied by linguists. Moreover, it is about the life of mankind, the role and importance of concepts of nature in the English language, the center of which is sheds light on elementary concepts about.

Keywords: eco linguistics, ecological terminology, parable, matal, fable.

Various changes have been occurring in the world since XX and XXI centuries. Transformations in industry, production, in labor activity of a person getting into everyday contact with nature and these actions have its own results and consequences. Which, in turn, are creating new terms in Ecology. For example, the word deforestation is in English the language began to be used from the second quarter of the XIX century. Earlier 1530 1435- in the years, this word expresses the transformation of forests into another area, it was a word of legislation and was used in the form of deforesting. "Ecological the selection of nominations is carried out in accordance with the EPBC Act. New name submitted to the committee and considered." [1]

Main part: Eco linguistics are divided into two types that completely contradict each other and eco linguist means a scientist that studies nature and language. This is the science of language on nature learners. For example, the language tools used in advertising are for us to buy products that are not first-class and are not harmful to nature. Because the life of human beings is precisely associated with nature and eco. Eco linguistics, on the other hand, refers to the motives aimed at preserving the nature of human beings with the creation of motivating speeches, phrases, quotes,

New neologisms Happy as a pig in muck. - Endless joy. Over the moon-cannot fit into joy. The world is your oyster. - Living taking advantage of the opportunities in life must. The above phrases are used to describe the state of mind of people. In English people, such as pigs, dogs, cats, domesticated and it is among the animals to be cared for. Words Dog, cat, pig many English phrases can be found that have taken part in daily speeches. It's raining cats and dogs - it's raining in buckets. (There's) More Than one Way to Skin A Cat. - Even snow if you find special part of it burns. The English Meaning of the phrase in the given source will be explained. There are multiple ways to do this task. Example: Joe's user interface did not work well, but there's more than one way to skin a cat [9]. We can also find ecological words in Proverbs and sayings. The English term fabula, fable in the language correspond to parables and matalas in the Uzbek language. By using them people can get the chance to illuminate shortcomings, injustices in society. from the above examples, the strangeness between nature and man, and this dependence we can see some of the points that have moved to the language.

Pronouns are used in languages to prevent us from repeating words. In order to adress third person there are three different forms of pronouns that represent unity:

1. He-humans for the male sex.
2. She-men for the female sex.
3. Dog-for inanimate objects and items.

While expressing ecological terms, people rely on likeness, fact, usage, and position.

For example:

methane (CH₄) - A hydrocarbon that is a greenhouse gas with a global warming potential most recently estimated at 23 times that of carbon dioxide (CO₂) [8]. Hydrocarbon, carbon dioxide, nature gases to interpret the word methane it is necessary to understand more deeply the meaning of his words. Hydrocarbon, carbon dioxide, nature gases to interpret the word methane it is necessary to understand more deeply the meaning of his words.

In conclusion, we will say that phraseological gadgets are extraordinarily essential components of linguistics in any language. Additionally, using idioms is so not unusual place with inside the discipline of translation because it has greater advantages for translators and interpreters. But, whilst translating them from one language into any other they must be cautious approximately their which means and take note of locate the maximum appropriate equal of those idioms in place of translating them phrase for phrase.

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